
THE HAITIAN PRESIDENT'S ASSASSINATION AND ITS AFTERMATH DIPLOMATICALLY.

1) INTRODUCTION

Haiti recently went through a vast event: the assassination of Haitian President Jovenel Moise, a former businessman aged 53 years old. President Moise took the Haitian office in 2017 was shot and assassinated along with his wife Martine Moise, who was seriously wounded yet survived. According to Haitian national officials, a few heavily armed assassins stormed into the home of the President in the early hours of July 7th around 1 a.m. in their local time. According to the ambassador of Haiti to the United States, Bocchit Edmond, the gunmen were masquerading as the DEA (the United States Drug Enforcement Administration) agents when they silently entered the guarded residence of Moise under cover of the nightfall¹.

The assassination of the president had deteriorated the country's political, social, economic states as well as introduced several devastating political issues and turmoil, extremely poor socio-economic state of the overall country, confusion, and chaos in the streets due to increased violent activities of local gangs as well as large armed organizations, less clarity about the legal succession order. Unrest continued due to the proclamation made by one of the most powerful leaders of a Haitian gang which entailed that the gang's members would protest as well as take to the streets due to the assassination and their prime objective was to rally against the opposition politician members and the Haitian national officials as the leader accuses these individuals and groups of having colluded with the "stinking bourgeoisie" so as to "sacrifice" President Moise². According to many experts, the circumstances surrounding President Jovenel Moise's assassination remain opaque to this day as conflicting theories about the culprits emerge from everywhere. However, the National Police of Haiti did mention that 28 mercenaries or former soldiers carried out the murder and the prime suspect remains a doctor from Florida, Christian Emmanuel Sanon, who wanted to take the presidential chair.

Several diplomatic situations followed in the aftermath of the assassination of Haitian President Moise, and it is mainly related to their diplomatic relations and past experiences with the United States, all of which will be analyzed and carefully described in the sections that follow. The paper also aims to provide a few recommendations as to what actions and/ or policies can be incorporated to remedy the diplomatic as well as the political situation of Haiti.

¹ IVAN NAVARRO, "Last Viewed Blogs," *power* 23 (2020): 1.

² Matthew Cole and Kim Ives, "Haiti: US Mercenaries Caught Moving \$80 M from Petrocaribe Fund," *Green Left Weekly*, no. 1218 (2019): 14–15.

PROBLEM SITUATION

The opaque conditions behind the assassination of the Haitian President Jovenel Moise make the circumstances more intense as it abounds more conflicting theories about the culprits and other situations and details about the assassination. The execution was allegedly carried out by a squad of 28 mercenaries and some former soldiers or military veterans in the early hours of July 7th, according to the Haitian police. The authorities have killed three individuals who were alleged suspects and have arrested another squad of twenty, including two Haitian American individuals and eighteen former soldiers from Colombia³. Five suspects are still on the run and are missing. The Haitian national authorities accused a doctor based in Florida, Christian Emmanuel Sanon, of plotting the entire assassination through a private security corporation located in Miami⁴.

The national authorities have further issued warrants for arrest on 13th July on charges of armed robbery as well as murder for a businessman named Rodolphe Jaar, the former senator named John Joel Joseph who was also one of the opponents of the Tet Kale party of Moise, and lastly an anti-corruption unit official named Joseph Felix Badio⁵. Further allegations were placed, and police took the president's security head to custody on July 15th. Authorities have also detained three more local security officials, as well as preventing many more from going overseas for the time being. Even after all of the events, the Haitian public's mistrust in the narratives of what happened on July 7th night does not appear to have subsided.

Many individuals and observers question why there is no emergence of any evidence, which clarifies why the security forces for the President and his family resisted the attacks completely, and only the dead and seriously injured bodies of the President and his wife were found⁶. Many individuals, as well as experts, have questioned how the Haitian authorities were able to quickly apprehend and capture the eighteen Colombian retired soldiers from their homes where they had been living and staying for the past one month, and how they were woefully underprepared for the probability that they could be found easily⁷. Further adding to the ambiguity is that the family members of all of the

³ F. Henry, "The Slow Rise of Social Movement Organizations for Memorialization in Haiti: Lutte Contre Impunite, Devoire de Memoire-Haiti and Digitizing the Record on Atrocities," in *Mass Violence and Memory in the Digital Age* (Springer, 2020), 175–196.

⁴ JUDITH MIRKINSON, "HAITI" (2019).

⁵ Christopher Davis, "History as an Enemy and an Instructor: Lessons Learned from Haiti, 1915–34," *Journal of Advanced Military Studies* 11, no. 1 (2020): 32–43.

⁶ Ed Morales, *Puerto Rico in Crisis* (NATION CO INC 33 IRVING PLACE, 8TH FLOOR, NEW YORK, NY 10003 USA, 2017).

⁷ Jon Western, "Independent Diplomat: Dispatches from an Unaccountable Elite. By Carne Ross. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2007. 243p. \$25.00.," *Perspectives on Politics* 7, no. 2 (2009): 450–451.

apprehended Colombians have stated that they were hired for protection for the Haitian President in the midst of a gang violence wave in Port-au-Prince⁸.

Diplomatic relations intervened, and the United States and the Colombian governments sent law enforcement experts to the region of Port-au-Prince to investigate the Haitian President's assassination. Another remarkable feature was that when Colombian security authorities and the media presented their perspectives and thoughts about the possible involvement of Haiti's interim Prime Minister, Claude Joseph, although the Colombian police chief flatly denied them, fuelling the probing into the matter⁹.

The wake of the Haitian President's assassination was followed by extreme uncertainty, turmoil, and violence. There were ambiguity and complications everywhere, starting from the country's political to socio-economic status, which was already damaged from before due to the poor mismanagement of Covid-19 and other affairs during the Moise presidency.

After the murder of the President, there was extremely little clarity over the legal succession order when the acting Haitian prime minister, Claude Joseph, self-proclaimed as the interim President and stated that the national authorities were handling as well as in control of the circumstances¹⁰. Although the Haitian constitution of 1987 said that presidency vacancy must be fulfilled by the head of the Supreme court, owing to the COVID-19 related death of the supreme court head and uncertainty regarding the next most senior judge of the country.

The matter of legal succession was made more complicated because of Moise's appointment of Ariel Henry as the seventh and new prime minister, but he had not been sworn in for certain reasons¹¹. On July 7th, Henry also self-declared as acting President and requested Joseph to take the role of foreign minister. Simultaneously, Henry voiced his promise to the political dialogue and joined a meeting of Joseph due to a delegation from the Government of the United States. The world diplomats, organizations, and core group of the states have been analyzing and discussing the Haitian crisis within New York (consisting of Canada, Brazil, Europe, Germany, France, Spain, the OAS, United States, and the United Nations Secretariat) finally called for the development and formation of a

⁸ Andreas Feldmann, "Examining the Root Sources of Violence in Haiti: Tracing the Relation between Structure and Contingency" (2019).

⁹ Chelsey L. Kivland, "'The People' Exposed: Spatio-Racial-Affective Alterity in Haitian Popular Protest," *Latin American and Caribbean Ethnic Studies* 15, no. 3 (2020): 219–244.

¹⁰ Archange Deshommes, *Democracy for the Haitian Crisis: Ideas for Political Reforms in Haiti* (AuthorHouse, 2020).

¹¹ Mariana Dos Santos Parra, "Building or Breaking the Polity? International Intervention, Statebuilding and Reproduction of Crisis in Haiti (2004–2019)," *Revista de Ciencia Política* 40, no. 2 (2020): 351–378.

government that is inclusive and consensus¹². They put Henry up to the task as well as encouraged him to put it together. The diplomatic military interventions were also affected due to the previous army intervention failures of the United States when they aimed to promote improvements within Haiti that will last¹³.

ACADEMIC KNOWLEDGE AND CONTENT INFORMATION

The previous actions of the states and the diplomatic organizations resulted in Joseph handing the power over to Henry and stepping down from his Prime Minister post on July 20th. The aftermath of the Haitian President's assassination and the political instability led to the reverse development of the security conditions as it became more grim. The immediate risks of street violence and the rise in unmanageable criminal activity will only give rise to further political instability¹⁴. This will further escalate into something a thousand times worse specifically if individuals and gang members find out that the powerful and political rice figures have deep-rooted involvement in the assassination of the president¹⁵. The powerful and violent gangs within Haiti who are almost always linked with business and political forces have grown significantly in both influence and strength and pose a significant threat to the overall integrity and security of any elections that will be held in the upcoming days¹⁶. Several incidences were considered to be significant by major United Nations organizations as well as other diplomatic heads, which included reported rise in murders, rapes, armed gang activities, and violence which has impeded the ability of the UN Office of Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs to distribute the humanitarian assistance which they aimed to provide which also included suspending and/or canceling a program that was designed to distribute money to approximately 30,000 individuals, if not more¹⁷.

The concept of diplomats and outside actors is also somewhat conspicuous. Several external actors, including the United States of America, have provided clear indications

¹² Keegan C. Krause, "Stigma in Paradise: Experiences of Young Haitian Im/Migrant Men with Structural Violence, Occupational Health, and Social Capital in the Informal Tourism Sector of the Dominican Republic" (The University of Arizona, 2020).

¹³ Nicolas Scheffer, "Infrastructural Violence and the Afterlives of Road Building: Creating a Haitian Space in 20th Century Occupied Haiti" (The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, 2020).

¹⁴ Kacper Grass, "Direct Military Intervention and Stability in the United States' Backyard, 1965-1995" (2018).

¹⁵ Geoff R. Berridge, *Diplomacy: Theory and Practice* (Springer, 2015).

¹⁶ Helena Arvidsson, "Cholera: Anthropology and Epidemiology," 2018.

¹⁷ Kim Ives, "Trump Triggers Haiti Revolt," *Green Left Weekly*, no. 1209 (2019).

that they have a strong desire to avoid any interventions within the country that are bold in nature. Interim president Joseph had requested military assistance and interventions from the United States, which was rebuffed by the US officials owing to their prior failures regarding the military interventions to make lasting improvements to the conditions within Haiti¹⁸. Previous experiences about failed military interventions of the United States included the 1994 US intervention where the focus was to restore the presidency of Jean Bertrand Aristide by deposing the military of Junta that originally ousted the President. However, only ten years later, the army intervened again due to a Haitian gang rebellion that led to escorting the still President Aristide into exile through extremely controversial situations. President Joe Biden further confirmed the decision on July 15th to state that they were not entertaining the idea of sending American military forces into Haiti¹⁹.

Even the Security Council of the UN does not seem willing to significantly increase the United Nation's overall presence in the Haiti situation. This decision can also be traced back to another diplomatic position that included a significant stabilization mission within Haiti (named MINUSTAH) that addressed the massive violations of human rights and the rampant insecurity within Haiti after their acting President Aristide took flight.

Further literature suggests that the mission of MINUSTAH achieved quick and early success in the areas of police and authoritative reforms and stabilizing the regions that were highly affected by gang violence and criminal activity primarily due to the assistance and significant contribution of the Brazilian military. Although the allegations that were placed on the troops and military personnel plagued the entire mission, allegations were made regarding the excessive use of force, being responsible for bringing about the cholera epidemic just following the wake of the earthquake in 2010 and committing several cases of abuse of sexual nature. The allegations were so loud and started to gain rapid consensus, which led to the Secretary-General's office finally acknowledging the role of the United Nations in the outbreak of cholera. The mission of MINUSTAH eventually succeeded in the year 2019 by the United Nation Integrated Office within Haiti (BINUH), which was a comparatively low-key political mission that primarily focused on providing very limited assistance as well as advising the local authorities on how to accomplish violence reduction as well as to attain political stability²⁰.

The Security Council of the United Nations also had discussed the situation of Haiti privately after the assassination of President Moïse. However, there seems to be a lack thereof of consensus even within the Core Council group about further enhancing the mission. On the contrary, some members from the Council appears to be drawn as well as entertaining the idea of strengthening the ability of the mission to provide strong electoral support and assistance much ahead of the planned polls in September, which is also a significant part of the mission's mandate given the limited capacity of the mission, majority

¹⁸ Anthony Kwame Harrison, "The Time of Our Lives," *General Anthropology* 27, no. 2 (2020): 1–5.

¹⁹ Shawn Dorman, *Inside a US Embassy: Diplomacy at Work, All-New, of the Essential Guide to the Foreign Service* (Potomac Books, Inc., 2011).

²⁰ Oxford Analytica, "COVID-19 Threatens High Death Toll in Haiti," *Emerald Expert Briefings*, no. oxandb (n.d.).

of others believe that the BINUH mission would better achieve their goals through supporting the thorough diplomatic efforts to lessen the huge gap between the Haitian social as well as political forces²¹.

The current state of Haiti has been plunged into massive unrest and turmoil and major prevalence of chaos²². Nearly 40 per cent of the Haitian population faces food insecurity in acute nature, rampant conditions of violence and crimes, a political process that is completely frozen, and refuses to take any major steps without outside intervention. In a situation like this, BINUH should be taking valued lessons from MINUSTAH as well as should be focusing more on conducting an extensive study of the crisis as well as its origins and then work together collaboratively with the country team of the United Nations as well as the current Government controlling Haiti to address as well as tackle the root causes²³.

Several diplomatic representatives have warned that there might be renewed without an immediate political settlement, followed by the concomitant breakdown of law and order, which will most definitely result in the regions having detrimental effects. Thus, in this respect, even the member states of the Caribbean Community (CARICOM) are also bound by duty as well as the responsibility to assist their sister Caribbean country find a resolution to its issues in a peaceful manner as well as can continue their daily operations in a manner which is far less chaotic than current situations²⁴. Several areas still need to be addressed in deep, and according to the representatives of Haiti, the newly appointed Government Henry continues to work hard towards finding strategies to solve the issues of the political impasse, restoring the overall authority of the state across the entire span of the country, tackle the overall gang violence as well as crimes²⁵.

Further diplomatic issues arise owing to the sexual abuse and exploitation that Haiti had to go through years ago due to the United Nation's troops. However, the new Government is highly encouraged and motivated by the United Nations emphasis on a zero-tolerance approach towards sexual abuse and exploitation during several important peacekeeping missions and operations within Haiti²⁶. Although owing to what has already been done historically, the nation feels specifically worried due to the abandonment that

²¹ Oxford Analytica, "Gang Alliance Heightens Political Concerns in Haiti," *Emerald Expert Briefings*, no. oxan-db (n.d.).

²² Western, "Independent Diplomat: Dispatches from an Unaccountable Elite. By Carne Ross. Ithaca, NY: Cornell University Press, 2007. 243p. \$25.00."

²³ Oxford Analytica, "Haiti Unrest Will Cripple Moise's Government in 2019," *Emerald Expert Briefings*, no. oxan-db (n.d.).

²⁴ Oxford Analytica, "Haiti Police Unrest Exacerbates COVID-19 Challenges," *Emerald Expert Briefings*, no. oxan-es (2020).

²⁵ Ronald Peter Barston, *Modern Diplomacy* (Routledge, 2019).

²⁶ Jean-Robert Leguey-Feilleux, *The Dynamics of Diplomacy* (Lynne Rienner Publishers Boulder, CO, 2009).

the orphans will feel who were fathered by the peacekeepers from the United Nations²⁷. Therefore, the aim is to help the victims through transparency of operations and rigor. The Government, as well as other relevant authorities and leaders, are already aware of all the political, social as well as economic issues that have engulfed the country after the assassination of President Moïse as well as are also aware of the several fragile as well as complex situations with diplomatic relations. Although what is necessary and required at this hour and is expected is that political leaders and actors will show their selflessness aspect in finding some lasting improvements and solutions and forging dialogues that are real and honest.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Some recommendations for the situation of Haiti as well as its diplomatic aftermath due to the assassination of the Haitian President Moïse includes;

- Although diplomatic, military assistance, and intervention are well-advised to be wary, it is most vital to assist Haiti in overcoming and recovering from the intimidating security challenges within the country. The missions should be mainly focused on building up the police and national authority force
- According to experts, almost 21,000 officers are short within the national and local police forces, which should be boosted by introducing new and faster forms of training. The efforts should also be spared intensively to make the forces more humane, professional, and reputable in nature and their work and conduct.
- The country also needs to achieve political consensus about a reform agenda that will be proposed only after wide agreement. This reform agenda will gain political stability and success in several functions.
- Other areas of improvement may pertain to taking actions that may include addressing the widespread gang violence and crimes and promoting human rights for all individuals inhabiting the country irrespective of their cultural and regional backgrounds.
- The Government and the assistance of outside interventions such as BINUH can help address the socioeconomic and unemployment grievances surrounding the nation to provide a basis for constant development and growth.

²⁷ Brian Concannon, "JISB Interview: Cholera, Accountability, and the UN in Haiti," *Journal of Intervention and Statebuilding* 12, no. 1 (2018): 142–154.

- The state should also be encouraged to be present in specific communities, especially those under certain issues and problems, and contribute by providing essential services.
- Corruption is a deeply ingrained issue within the political system of Haiti, where individuals can become millionaires simply by joining the Government and spending a few years in it. Thus, Security Council, in collaboration with the court and parliament, can work to develop effective policies to strengthen the institutional and normative frameworks of Haitian politics. Good governance can also help the country improve and maintain peace, stability, and socioeconomic abundance without much help from diplomatic relations and sources.
- The local and national authority within Haiti should aim to take down the primary gang organizations within Haiti to lessen violence and crimes and promote security and peace along with equal human rights. The Government can also form policies that diminish the sale of arms and ammunition out in the open and other illegal things.
- The supreme court must play an imperative part in prosecuting all the major gangs and organizations irrespective of the association with top political authorities.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, it can be concluded from above that the state of Haiti was extremely bad due to issues and problems within their politics and political actions, which was further obliterated by the assassination of President Jovenel Moise and his wife being gravely injured. The situation grew exponentially and started to spread out from every possible direction and contributed to adverse developments all around the nation. The conspicuous and murky way the President was murdered called for even bigger conflicting theories that even pertained to other political leaders and actors being associated with the plan that enraged several gang organizations within Haiti. This further gave way for increased gang violence, street crimes and unrest, and chaos everywhere. United Nations and outside reports suggest that criminal activities of murder, corruption, sexual assault and rape, and other things increased significantly.

This was further exhumed by the Security Council of the United Nations, but they were unwilling to proceed with any major interventions due to their previous failures in promoting stability and peace through military interventions and support. The missions had been met with a lot of allegations and criticism due to the way troops acted in the regions and due to these reasons, the outside diplomatic nations, organizations, and bodies have fundamentally refused to intervene in any major revelation or intervention within the Haiti but has been providing help and assistance to their representatives.

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